

A Review of Effect of *Udumbar* on *Shwitra Kushta*

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ABSTRACT

Shwitra is a type of skin disorder. It can be compared with Vitiligo according to modern science. [1] Shwitra, Kilas, Varun, Darun are the synonyms in ayu texts. Whitish discolouration of the skin is main sign in the disease. According to ayu.texts Udumbar i.e. *Ficus racemosa* has very good action on the Shvitrakushtha. According to Ayurveda Udumbar is digest), Rooksha(dry), Katu(pungent in taste), Tikta(bitter). Also taste conversion after digestion is Katu(Pungent) and hot potency. Due to all this factors Udumbar helps in breaking the pathology of Shwitra as Balances Kapha & Vata. Also according to modern pharmacology *Ficus racemosa* has astringent, antidiabetic, refrigerant, action.

Key words- Shwitra, Udumbar, Laghu, Tikta, Katu, Rooksha

INTRODUCTION

[2] Shwitra is a type of skin disorder .It is described as a type of Kushtha. Main sign of this disease is whitish discolouration of the skin. It can be correlated with Vitiligo modern science. In modern science Kushta can be correlated with Leprosy. Leprosy is a contagious disorder. Shwitra do not spread due to skin contact, so it is not contagious disease. Hereditary factors play an important role in this disease. Udumbar can be advised in Shwitra according to Samhitas.

Shwitra

In Shwitra all the three doshas are involved. [3] Synonyms of Shwitra are Kilas, Varun according to some texts and some Samhitas mentioned these as the types of it. According to the site disease manifests symptoms i.e. patches are reddish, coppery and white in color. In Charak Samhitait is mentioned that if it gives reddish color the doshas are located in rakta. I fit gives coppery colors the doshas are located in

mamsa dhatu. White colour will be produced if the doshas are situated in the med dhatu..

Etiology-

[4] As mentioned in ayu texts Shwitra and Kushta both are skin diseases and both have the same aetiology. Untruthfulness, ungratitude, abusing gods, insulting teachers, indulging sinful acts, sinful deeds of previous birth, and consumption of mutually contradictory food. Worms are mentioned as main causative factor. Shwitra is found spreading in the family.

Pathology

Involvement of doshas and dhatus is the main difference in Shivtra and Kushta. Tvakdhatu involvement is the main in Shwitra and in Kushta all dhatus are involved. Sushruta also mentioned involvement of only skin dhatu.

Signs and symptoms-

- Discoloration of the skin is the main sign of shvitra.
- No secretions and itching rashes are seen in the Shvitra.

Types

- 1) Vranaj (after any type of wound) mainly dagdhavrana (burns).
- 2) Doshas i.e. involvement of doshas.

In doshas type difference between signs and symptom is observed

Vatajshvitra- Patches are rough and red in color and destroying the skin.

Pittajshvitra- Patches are light red in color having burning sensation

Kaphajshvitra- Patches are white unctuous, thick and itching.

Prognosis- [5] According to Madhavnidan Incurable-

1. The patches are mutually matted together
2. Having multiple lesions
3. Surrounded by red hair
4. Chronic duration.

Curable-

1. The patches are surrounded by non redish hair having
2. Thin white lesion
- 3 Recent onset along
- 4 Elevated margins between two patches.

Vitiligo-

According to modern science we can compare Shvitra with Vitiligo .Melanin is the pigment which gives black color to the skin. Whitish color to the skin is due to absence of this Melanin. This is called as Vitiligo. Vitiligo do not spread due to skin contact. This is found in families. Some theories say that this is auto immune disorder.

Some theories say that food items like Oranges, lemon etc food rich in Vit. C and Ascorbic acid also fermented food items as curd, alcohol, fish, red meat can prove harmful on vitiligo. So it should be avoided. Allopathic science says that it is not curable. Along with some pathyapathya (diet regimes) ayurvedic texts give some remedies

Udumbar

[6] Udumbar can also prove very efficient and usefull in Shvitra.

Latin name –Ficusracemosa

Family –Urticaceae.

Synonyms – According to morphology and actions

Jantufal, Yadnyang, Hemdugdhak, Kashak, Ks irvriksha, Sadafal, Yadniy, Supratishtit, Shitva lka, Soumya,

Kshiri, these are the synonyms mentioned in ayurvedic texts

[7] According to ayurveda

Ras(taste)-Kashay (bitter), Madhur(sweet)

Post digestion effect -Katu(pungent).

Virya (potency) –Shita(cold)

Guans (qualities) –Guru(heavy) roksha (dry or rough).

All these qualities make Udumbar ranaropak, varnya. Also Shvitraghna i.e. helps in curing shvitra. It can be used in kapha pitta diseases. It can be used in wound healing. [8] It has specific anti-inflammatory property. Also it is specifically an irritant or it can gives relief from burning sensation. It is used to increase complexion. It can be used as antinflammatory and also pain killer.

[9] Due to post digestion effect and potency it is Stambhak (it obstruct the excessive movement of stool) agnisad (it decreases power of agni). So it can be used in diarrhea, dysentery, Also it can be used in small children in which diarrhea is due to teeth eruption period. As it decreases appetite it can be used in bhasmak (hyper bilemia)

According to ayurvedic texts it can travel through the blood i.e. Raktagami, So it can be used in rakta pitta (haemoptysis, hemorrhoids) in this it can stop bleeding through various openings. In Jaundice also it can be used.

It also acts on reproductive system. It can decrease inflammation of uterus. So it can be used in menorrhagia, white discharge, dysmenorrhoea. Deccocution can be used for development of foetus.

^[10] Stambhak property can be used in urinary system. It can prevent excess urine frequency. So can be used in Diabetes.

So from doshagnata property we can conclude that Udumbar decreases pitta, and kapha. Also it can travel through blood. Also it can prevent abortion

CONCLUSION

Due to bitter and sweet taste, cold potency udumbar is Kaphaghna and pittaghna. As in Shvitra tridosh dushti is observed udumbar helps in breaking the pathology of Shvitra. Also anti-inflammatory, and varnya qualities help in improving the shvitraghna properties. Udumbar proves very much effective in Shvitra.

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